

The relationship of trust to the willingness to do COVID-19 vaccination in coastal communities in Tanjung Pinang village, Muna Barat district

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Abstract

The low percentage of vaccine acceptance in the community in West Muna Regency is inseparable from the presence of influencing factors, one of which is due to the perception of the community itself. There are still people who refuse to give the COVID-19 vaccine because public awareness of the importance of vaccination for the community is still low, rumors are circulating that the COVID-19 vaccine (Sinovac) contains a dangerous vaccine, and the source comes from China, which incidentally is the source of the COVID-19 virus. In addition, people's lack of understanding about the purpose, benefits of vaccination, and what effects will be caused if they don't vaccinate can be another reason why people don't want to get vaccinated. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between trust in the willingness to vaccinate against COVID-19 in Coastal Communities in Tanjung Pinang Village, West Muna Regency to the willingness to vaccinate COVID-19. This type of research is a quantitative study using a cross-sectional study design method. The method of data collection is done by the method of distributing questionnaires and field observations. Implementation Data analysis was carried out using Univariate and Bivariate Analysis. The results of the study indicate that there is a significant relationship between trust in the willingness to carry out the COVID-19 Vaccine in Coastal Communities in Tanjung Pinang Village, West Muna Regency with a p-value ($0.028 < 0.05$). The conclusion of the variable Trust affects the willingness to carry out COVID-19 Vaccination in Coastal Communities in Tanjung Pinang Village, West Muna Regency. A suggestion is hoped that the government will intensify socialization regarding the importance of the COVID-19 vaccination in collaboration with local health workers.

Keywords: Trust; COVID-19; Vaccine; Vaccination

1. Introduction

At the end of December 2019, it began with a case of pneumonia of unknown etiology in Wuhan, China. Based on the results of epidemiological data, the case is suspected to be related to the Seafood Market in Wuhan. Then on January 7, 2020, the Chinese government announced that the cause of the case was a new type of coronavirus which was later named SARS-CoV-2 (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2). This virus comes from the same family as the viruses that cause SARS and MERS. Even though it comes from the same family, SARS-CoV-2 is more contagious than SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV [1]. The rapid transmission process led WHO to designate COVID-19 as KKMM/PHIEC (Public Health Emergency of International Concern) on January 30, 2020. Vaccines are one of the most effective and economical ways to prevent infectious diseases. So it is necessary to develop a vaccine to make it more effective at weakening the coronavirus infection. So far more than 40 pharmaceutical companies and academic institutions around the world have launched their vaccine development programs against the COVID-19 virus [2].

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As of December 9, 2020, WHO has reported 67,530,912 confirmed cases of COVID-19 globally and 1,545,140 deaths and has been affected in 220 countries³. Meanwhile, the COVID-19 situation in Indonesia, according to data from the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia on 9 December 2020, continues to increase and has been affected in 502 Regencies/Cities, 306 Local Transmissions with a total of 592,900 positive confirmed cases, 487,445 recovered cases, 18,171 deaths, and suspected cases. as many as 69,879 [3].

The Ministry of Health together with several organizations (ITAGI, UNICEF, and WHO) conducted an online survey on 19-30 September 2020 to find out about public acceptance of the COVID-19 vaccine. The survey involved more than 115,000 respondents from 34 provinces in Indonesia. Based on the survey, it is known that 658 respondents are willing to accept the COVID-19 vaccine if provided by the Government, while 8% of them refuse. The remaining 274 expressed doubts about the Government's plan to distribute the COVID-19 vaccine. Based on respondent data conducted by the Ministry of Health together with the Indonesian Technical Advisory Group on Immunization (ITAGI) which was released in October 2020, it shows that there is still around 7.6 percent of people who refuse to be vaccinated and 26.6 percent of people have not decided yet and are still confused [4].

The coverage of dose 1 vaccination in Southeast Sulawesi province has reached 73.1 percent. This figure is equivalent to 1.46 million participant's vaccine of the set target of 2 million people. The first dose of vaccine coverage for the elderly is 62.17%. The general public 78.66%, public officers 68.03%, health human resources 129.79%, and children aged 12-17 as much as 91.93% Meanwhile, for dose 2 vaccination, 64.30% of the target has been achieved which includes the elderly as much as 43.00%, the general public 55.85%, public officers 59.65%, health human resources 125.23% and children aged 12-17 years 67.57%. Whereas for the West Muna Regency Region, the coverage of vaccination until December 31 2021 was 46,010 for dose one, and 16,824 for dose two, out of 64,128 targets targeted [5].

The management of the COVID-19 virus has received recommendations from WHO for measures to prevent the spread of COVID-19, including practicing hand hygiene, social distancing, wearing masks, and increasing endurance. Many things can be done to increase endurance, one of which is consuming nutritious food, exercising, avoiding stress, and taking health supplements [6].

From the description above, the researcher wants to know more about the relationship between knowledge, family support, and trust in the willingness to do the COVID-19 vaccine in the coastal community of Tanjung Pinang Village, West Muna Regency.

2. Methodology

The method used in this research is quantitative with a cross-sectional study design using a questionnaire. Determination of the sample in this study using probability sampling by using a simple random sampling technique, namely sampling from the population is done randomly without regard to strata in the population, the sample size used is 100 samples. Data analysis techniques were carried out using univariate analysis and bivariate analysis. The data presentation technique is carried out in the form of a frequency distribution accompanied by an explanation

3. Research result

3.1. Univariate Analysis

3.1.1. Trust

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents Based on Community Trust in Tanjung Pinang Village, West Muna Regency

No	Trust	Amount (n)	Percent (%)
1	Not good	19	19.0
2	Well	81	81.0
Total		100	100.0

Data Source: Primary Data, 2022

Public confidence in administering the COVID-19 vaccine both from a religious and medical perspective in Tanjung Pinang, West Muna Regency. The distribution of respondents based on community knowledge in Tanjung Pinang, West Muna Regency, can be presented in table 1.

Table 1 shows that out of 100 respondents, 19 people (19.0%) had poor confidence and 81 people (81.0%) had good confidence.

3.2. Willingness to Do the COVID-19 Vaccine

The willingness of the public to carry out the COVID-19 vaccine at health service facilities in Tanjung Pinang, West Muna Regency. The distribution of respondents based on community knowledge in Tanjung Pinang, West Muna Regency, can be seen in table 2:

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents Based on Willingness to Do COVID-19 vaccine in Tanjung Pinang Village, West Muna Regency

No	Willingness to Vaccine	Amount (n)	Percent (%)
1	Not willing	23	23.0
2	Ready	77	77.0
	Total	100	100.0

Data Source: Primary Data, 2022

Based on table 2, shows that out of 100 respondents, there were 23 people (23.0%) were not willing to do the COVID-19 vaccine, while 77 people (77.0%) were willing.

3.3. Bivariate Analysis

Trust in vaccination is a relationship that exists between individuals, as well as between individuals and systems, in which one party accepts a vulnerable position, assuming the best interests and competencies of the other, in return for reducing the complexity of the decision. rejecting vaccinations, the social acceptance of vaccines, and societal trust in science. The results of the relationship test between the trust variable and the willingness to do the COVID-19 vaccine can be seen in table 3:

Table 3 The relationship of trust to the willingness to do COVID-19 vaccination in coastal communities in Tanjung Pinang village, Muna barat district

Trust	Willingness to do the COVID-19 vaccine				Total		Pearson correlation (r)	p.s-value
	Not willing		Ready		n	%		
	n	%	n	%				
Not good	8	4,4	11	14,6	19	100	0.22	0.028
Well	15	18,6	66	62,4	81	100		
Total	23	23.0	77	77.0	100	100		

Data source: Primary data 2022

Based on table 3 shows that out of 81 respondents (100%) who had good faith there were 66 respondents (62.4%) were willing to do the COVID-19 vaccine compared to those who were not willing 15 respondents (18.6%) and 19 respondents (100%) who have poor trust, there are 11 respondents (14.6%) who are willing to do the COVID-19 vaccine and respondents who are not willing are 8 respondents (4.4%).

Based on Pearson analysis calculations, it shows that trust has a value (r) = 0.22, meaning low correlation and value (p-value <0.05), then H0 is rejected, meaning that there is a significant relationship between trust and willingness to do the COVID-19 vaccine.

4. Discussion

Trust in vaccination is a relationship that exists between individuals, as well as between individuals and systems, in which one party accepts a vulnerable position, assuming the best interests and competencies of the other, in return for reducing the complexity of the decision. Rejecting vaccinations, the social acceptance of vaccines, and societal trust in science [7].

Factors that influence the level of public trust in the government are related to government activities. Activities issued by a policy formulation (statement of the objectives to be achieved) that concern internal government as well as those that concern the general public. In addition, implementing policies that include efforts to provide resources for implementing policies, making regulations, organizing implementation, and providing services and utilization of health [8].

The theory of planned behavior is that beliefs cannot influence behavior directly but because they are influenced by prior intentions, while intentions are influenced by attitudes and subjective norms [9]. Subjective norms are influenced by one's beliefs about the reactions of other people or groups to their behavior and motivation that meet their expectations [10]. Through this theory it can be concluded that acceptance related to the COVID-19 vaccination is determined by an assessment of trust or confidence in the behavior to be taken, so that self-control with the perception of the consequences that will occur when giving COVID-19 preventive measures, one of which is by taking a vaccine COVID-19 [9].

Public trust is also very related to a person's behavior because it is influenced by a high level of knowledge so it increases a high level of trust in someone to be willing to vaccinate COVID. In addition, the involvement of the community is also very important in the willingness to do the vaccine because there is encouragement from the local government.

The results of the study show that the trust of the people in the coastal areas is quite strong. This was influenced by the level of knowledge about the COVID-19 vaccine and encouragement from the local government to work with local health workers to plan information dissemination activities related to the COVID-19 vaccination either through direct counseling or through social media such as Facebook, Instagram, and WAG, to increase knowledge, trust and public acceptance of the COVID-19 vaccination program.

Based on the results of a bivariate study, it was found that there was a significant effect between trust and willingness to vaccinate against COVID-19, where if the trust is good, more people are also willing to vaccinate against COVID-19.

A theory that suggests that belief is related to a higher power, skill, or force that creates life. Aspects of belief in human life direct the culture of life, normal behavior, habits, values, and use of resources in a society that will produce a pattern of life called culture which has a deep influence on behavior [11].

Research that is in line states that there is a relationship between trust in the COVID-19 vaccine and acceptance of the COVID-19 vaccination program with a p-value of 0.000 and OR: 10.222 meaning that respondents with good belief in the COVID-19 vaccine have a 10.222 times greater chance of receiving the COVID-19 vaccination program compared to respondents with less confidence in the COVID-19 vaccine. Around 65% of respondents said they were willing to accept the COVID-19 vaccine, 8% refused and 27% had doubts, this was due to the different levels of trust in the community towards the COVID-19 vaccine due to limited information about the type of vaccine and its safety profile [12].

The results of other studies that are in line state that from the results of the hypothesis testing, an R (correlation) is 0.730 and an R (square) is 0.533. It is known that belief in the COVID-19 vaccine and vaccination intention has a positive and significant effect on each other. This means that the higher the confidence in the COVID-19 vaccine, the higher the intention to vaccinate [13].

The level of public trust in the performance of the central government in handling COVID-19 can be measured by respondents' assessments regarding the fulfillment of the duties of the central government in handling COVID-19 cases, such as providing health facilities, providing facilities and infrastructure to prevent transmission of COVID-19, making policies for handling COVID-19 cases. 19 as well as the provision of means of detecting the COVID-19 virus [14]

Even though public trust is good, there are still some people who still lack confidence in the COVID-19 vaccine. Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers and from questionnaires given, on average, some respondents answered that they still doubted the safety of vaccines and the halalness of vaccines which made them reluctant to do

vaccines. In addition, some respondents also answered that they did not agree that vaccination could stop the epidemic. that the pandemic will end on its own without the need for a vaccine. Besides that, the reason why some respondents lacked confidence but were willing to be vaccinated was due to the influence of their social environment where they just joined in because their neighbors were vaccinated besides that because they wanted to get COVID-19 assistance from government programs.

Solutions and efforts made by the government to increase public confidence in the implementation of the COVID-19 vaccine, namely increasing knowledge, attitudes, and actions of the community through advocacy policies regarding the COVID-19 vaccination. Advocacy contains a complete understanding of COVID-19 vaccination, assisting parties such as local governments, non-governmental organizations, academics, media, religious leaders, community leaders, and the private sector in providing information to the public so that it can influence attitudes and actions to support the implementation of the COVID-19 vaccination [15].

Health workers help increase knowledge, attitudes, and actions by providing education about the importance of vaccines in preventing the transmission of COVID-19, providing facilities and community empowerment such as providing social support. Health workers can understand people's thinking patterns. Promotive and preventive actions in providing easy-to-understand communication so that people can distinguish between true and false information. The actions of health workers can help the community make decisions in determining actions to follow the COVID-19 vaccine [15].

So that it is hoped that the government, which is working with health workers, will be more optimal in providing health education to increase public confidence regarding the COVID-19 vaccine so that people, especially in coastal areas, so that all people are willing to vaccinate COVID-19.

5. Conclusion

The results of the study showed that there was a significant influence between trust and willingness to do the COVID-19 vaccine in coastal communities in Tanjung Pinang Village, Muna Barat District. It is hoped that the government will intensify socialization regarding the importance of the COVID-19 vaccination in collaboration with local health workers. People should take care of their health, often consume nutritious food, and exercise frequently to avoid various diseases.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors in the making of this scientific article have no conflict of interest

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